

AGROTECHNOLOGY OF RICE CULTIVATION

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Annotatsiya. Mamlakatimizda sifatli va raqobatbardosh oziq-ovqat maxsulotlarini yetishtirish, sarflanayotgan tabiiy va moddiy resurslardan, zamonaviy va tejamkor texnologiyalar yordamida samarali foydalanish, avvalo, mamlakat oziq-ovqat strategiyasi yo'nalishlari talablarini bajarish va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, boshqa tomondan, korxonalarining mavjud mehnat, yer, suv, moddiy va moliyaviy resurslaridan, mulk shakllaridan qat'iy nazar, ular o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy munosabatlarni takomillashtirish asosida, oqilona foydalanish evaziga tarmoq samaradorligini oshirish muhim hisoblanadi.

Аннотация. Выращивание в нашей стране качественной и конкурентоспособной продовольственной продукции, эффективное использование потребляемых природных и материальных ресурсов с помощью современных и рентабельных технологий, в первую очередь, служит выполнению требований направлений продовольственной стратегии страны и обеспечению продовольствием. безопасность. Также, с другой стороны, важно повысить эффективность работы сети за счет рационального использования имеющихся трудовых, земельных, водных, материальных и финансовых ресурсов предприятий, независимо от форм собственности, на основе совершенствования экономических отношений. между ними.

Abstract. Cultivation of high-quality and competitive food products in our country, effective use of consumed natural and material resources with the help of modern and cost-effective technologies, first of all, serves to fulfill the requirements of the country's food strategy directions and ensure food safety. Also, on the other hand, it is important to increase the efficiency of the network through the rational use of existing labor, land, water, material and financial resources of enterprises, regardless of the forms of ownership, based on the improvement of economic relations between them.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy samaradorlik, rentabellik, asosiy ko'rsatkichlar, tizim, foyda, moddiy xarajat, daromad, ekin maydoni, yalpi mahsulot, xosildorlik, sof foyda, paxta tolasi, moliyaviy mablag'lar.

Ключевые слова: экономическая эффективность, рентабельность, основные показатели, система, преимущества, материальные затраты, доход, посевная площадь, валовой продукт, урожайность, чистая прибыль, хлопковое волокно, финансовые фонды.

Keywords: economic efficiency, profitability, key indicators, system, profit, material cost, income, cultivated area, gross product, productivity, net profit, cotton fiber, financial resources.

The decision of the President of February 2, 2021 "On measures to further develop rice cultivation" is important for our people, primarily because it serves this purpose and opens a wider way to ensure the abundance of the table. For this, it will be necessary to improve the system of rice cultivation, to provide stable supply of rice products to the domestic consumer market and to increase the export potential, to strengthen research and development activities in this regard, and to ensure the wide use of water-saving technologies.

Rice is grown under irrigation and crop rotation. In Uzbekistan, rice is planted in non-saline or saline areas in spring, Apr. is planted in the 2nd half of (in some countries, seedlings are grown as seedlings). In the conditions of Uzbekistan, 120-180 kg of 14, 120-150 kg of R205, 100-150 kg of K20 per hectare are applied to rice planting areas, the water is kept at the same rate, then it is increased to 10 cm. Watering is stopped when rice turns yellow. Ripe rice is harvested by combine harvesters. The seed of rice varieties planted in large areas should be renewed every 3-4 years. The storage period of seed rice usually does not exceed 2 years. Cereal products, especially rice, have been a symbol of sustenance and prosperity for our people since ancient times. It is not only one of the necessary food products, but also a source of satisfying the human body's need for carbohydrates and proteins, and is also the main feed for livestock, poultry, and fisheries.

It is not for nothing that it is said that Sarah is a seed. Because well-organized seed farming is an important condition for abundant harvest. In the decision, specific tasks were defined for the organization of rice seed farms and the establishment of a seed breeding system in them, the allocation of land areas, the strict approval of the planted seed areas in accordance with the established procedure, and the implementation of cleaning, sorting, and packing of seed rice in the farms.

It is known that rice grain (rice) has been cultivated in many countries of the world since ancient times and is one of the valuable products widely distributed and widely consumed on Earth. Among its hundreds of useful properties, it is the easiest to digest in the human body compared to other nutrients, its composition (proteins that are not found in other cereal crops), it is rich in vitamins and organic phosphorus compounds.

In our country, rice is still grown on irrigated lands, and climate changes have almost no effect on its productivity. It has been proven in practice that even in drought conditions, it is possible to obtain a higher yield if the required agrotechnologies are applied on time.

There are several methods of rice cultivation in world experience. In our republic, this crop is mostly grown on the basis of the technology of submerging the seeds in water. In this case, it is necessary to keep the water level in the rice plants at a thickness of 5-7, 10-12, 15-20 centimeters until the crop ripens.

According to research, quality rice seeds can increase productivity by up to 25 percent. For this, the initial germination level of elite 1st and 2nd reproduction seeds should be 85-95 percent. The quality of cultivated rice varieties is carried out by updating the variety. The seed of rice varieties planted in large areas should be renewed every 3-4 years. The shelf life of seed rice usually does not exceed 2 years. As defined in the decision, it will be possible to

achieve the expected effect by introducing a scientifically based crop rotation system to prevent the cultivation of rice in the field of seed farms for more than 2 years.

In recent years, in our country, special attention has been paid to the production of agricultural products, increase in export volume, application of modern technologies in the field, and rational use of water resources. Today, the increasing water shortage due to the increase in population and economic development on Earth requires the introduction of water-saving technologies in the cultivation of all crops, including rice.

If we pay attention to the data, an average of 52 billion cubic meters of water is consumed annually in the agricultural sector in our republic, 80% of which is contributed by transboundary rivers. Water in the territory of neighboring countries is formed due to the melting of glaciers and snow. However, as a result of climate change and other anthropogenic influences, the number and size of glaciers in the mountains has decreased sharply, and the volume of water in the rivers is decreasing. In addition, as a result of population growth and rapid economic development in the countries of the region, including Uzbekistan, the demand for water is increasing. In such conditions, the time demands the efficient and economical use of water resources in agriculture, especially the use of water-saving technologies in crop irrigation.

Although rice grows constantly in water, its water requirements vary throughout the growing season. In Uzbekistan, the irrigation period of sholipoyas, which is still traditionally planted, lasts from the third ten days of April to the first ten days of September.

The annual rate of irrigation is 16-25 thousand cubic meters per hectare depending on the climate, soil and the type of agrotechnical measures carried out in the traditional method, i.e. from the day the rice seeds are planted in the soil until they ripen. 30-40% of it is absorbed by the rice plant before the ripening period, and the rest is spent on useless aspects such as evaporation, absorption into the soil and going underground.

At present, water plants planted in the traditional way are watered with and without water. It is advisable to use the method of irrigation without draining water, which allows to save 25-30 percent of the annual water consumption. Importantly, this no-flow method can be used in non-saline or saline conditions.

A reduced irrigation method is used in conditions where rice seeds are sown to a depth of 1-2 centimeters using selkas. In this case, the first suppressed layer of water is kept for 3-4 days, and then watering is stopped. The layer of water on the floors is absorbed into the soil, and after the rows of grass are clearly visible, water is poured again in a layer of 5-6 centimeters. Under these conditions, it is possible to have the full number of seedlings per hectare of land and to save 2-3 thousand cubic meters of water per hectare.

One of the effective ways to save water is to grow rice by seedling method. In this method, a large part of the annual water requirement is saved due to the cultivation of rice seedlings in small areas.

At present, scientists and specialists of the Scientific Research Institute of Irrigation and Water Problems have prepared recommendations for the introduction of technologies for planting rice in the form of seedlings for use in the farms of farmers, peasants and landowners, and they are being distributed to rice farms in the republic.

Also, the leveling of land by techniques controlled by laser devices has become an urgent issue. Laser devices radically improve the quality of leveling works and increase technological indicators. In the process, geodetic work is reduced by 80%, aggregates'

productivity increases by 20-30%, productivity by 35%. Water consumption is reduced by 50%.

In the President's decision "On measures to further develop rice cultivation" in 2021, at least 20% of the total rice fields should be planted with seedlings, 50% of the land should be leveled using laser equipment, 30% should be planted with modern seed drills, 2022- it is planned to further increase these indicators. At present, land, water and other complex resources are available for quality implementation of all the above-mentioned issues in the practice of rice farming. Scientifically based technologies have been developed. Recommendations have been prepared and distributed to farmers and peasant households as a guide, training is being carried out.

In recent years, special attention has been paid to the production of agricultural products, increase in export, application of modern technologies in the field, and rational use of water resources. Ensuring the timely implementation of the measures specified in the decision should become the main daily task of us scientists, along with rice growing specialists, farmers, peasants, and farm land owners.

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